

Equilibrium of the Ternary System Bismuth Oxide, Hydrochloric Acid and Water.

BY

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Various hydrates of bismuth oxychloride have been described in the literature. Heintz [Pogg. Ann. 63, 55 (1884)] states that the precipitate first obtained by the addition of water to a solution of bismuth chloride containing hydrochloric acid is a monohydrate of bismuth oxychloride, which on keeping in a desiccator passes into the anhydrous oxychloride.

Phillips (Berz. Jahrsber. 11, 187) believes in the existence of a trihydrate of bismuth oxychloride, which he describes as occurring in tetragonal crystals.

Schulten [Bull. Soc. Chim. (3), 23, 156, 1900] describes a bihydrate of bismuth oxychloride.

The object of this paper is to account for divergence of opinion amongst different workers.

PREPARATION OF MATERIALS.

Bismuth Trioxide.—Bismuth trioxide was obtained by heating strongly crystals of bismuth nitrate carefully prepared.

Bismuth Trichloride.—Commercially pure bismuth trichloride was heated in a tube of the shape used by Faraday for liquefaction of gases, and the moisture sucked out by exhausting to 1 or 2 cm. pressure, while the bismuth trichloride was being heated. Then the open end of the tube was sealed. On heating more strongly bismuth trichloride partly distilled into the other arm as a yellow liquid and partly sublimed in white

crystals. The substance was kept in the sealed tube till required for use.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The solubility tubes were made by blowing an elongated bulb in the middle of a glass tube of 1 cm. bore and sealed at one end. The relative size of the bulb and its lower part was such that the solid phase separating out at the ordinary temperature could be contained in two-thirds of the lower tubular portion, and about one-third of the bulb was kept empty in order to ensure free mixing.

After filling and sealing the tubes, they were placed in a thermostat electrically maintained at 25°.

Equilibrium was attained in about 12 hours' shaking and after having allowed the solid phase to settle down, the tube was opened and the contents analysed.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS.

The clear liquid was sucked off with a small bulb-tube provided with a rubber tubing and a pinch-cock. It was weighed and dissolved in 1:1 sulphuric acid, and the solution made up to 50 c.c. When the bismuth content was great it was necessary to use somewhat stronger acid (2:1).

The composition of the solid phase was determined by Schreinmaker's method of residues.

Bismuth was precipitated as sulphide by passing H_2S to saturation in the dilute solution. The precipitate was filtered off, washed free of hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was dissolved in hot nitric acid and the ordinary process of precipitating with excess of ammonium carbonate, igniting the basic carbonate and weighing as Bi_2O_3 , was followed. The results obtained by this method were found correct to within 0.03%.

Chlorine was estimated by Volhard's method as modified by Rothmund and Burgstaller [Zeit. anorg. Chem., 63, 330 (1909)].

Varying amounts of sulphuric acid did not affect the results obtained in the estimation of chlorine as duplicate observations showed a difference in the third place of decimal.

The quadruple point was investigated by partially filling a solubility tube with a saturated solution of bismuth trichloride in hydrochloric acid; some solid trichloride was then introduced, and diluted with a few drops of water till the solution was just opalescent. When equilibrium was attained, the heterogenous solid phase, when seen under the microscope, was found to contain BiCl_3 crystals disseminated with an amorphous granular ppt.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

	Percentage Composition of Liquid Phase.		Percentage Composition of Solid Phase.		Nature of Solid Phase.
	Bi_2O_3	HCl.	Bi_2O_3	HCl.	
1	0.6%	2.50%	12.05%	4.05%	BiOCl .
2	2.60%	4.22%	19.40%	6.17%	"
3	11.44%	10.68%	26.26%	11.60%	"
4	13.16%	12.00%	25.40%	12.32%	"
5	16.41%	18.48%	27.53%	13.59%	"
6	23.76%	17.56%	31.30%	17.30%	"
7	26.42%	18.47%	28.63%	18.33%	"
8	50.74%	30.23%	53.41%	29.20%	"
9	58.72%	33.67%	Not analysed.		BiCl_3 .
10	58.70%	34.03%	"	"	"
11	58.59%	35.14%	62.04%	35.19%	"

CONCLUSION.

The results have been plotted in Roozeboom's triangle. From the tie lines it is manifest that they all intersect in the vicinity of one and only one point whose composition is given by $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3=89.2\%$, $\text{HCl}=13.8\%$, $\text{H}_2\text{O}=3.0\%$. By calculation the empirical formula of this compound is found to be $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{HCl}, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ or BiOCl . Thus it is evident that between the concentrations 25% and 33.67% of HCl, at 25°C, the only solid phase separating out consists of normal bismuth oxychloride. This is further confirmed by the non-existence of a break in the smooth isothermal curve joining the liquid points. This investigation shows that no hydrate of bismuth oxychloride exists, at least at the temperature of 25°.

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ISOTHERM at 25°C .

